

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report (acceptance note) for **TEBT-2024-0005**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Evidence-based approaches to managing Canadian oil sands tailing pond waste: tighter regulations and greater transparency are needed
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0005
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	2 peer-reviewers, 1 editorial review
Submission Type	Expert Commentary ▾
Preprint DOI	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11032000
Evaluation Date	11 Aug 2024
Evaluation Round	Acceptance note
Recommendation	Accept ▾
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	The authors' have responded satisfactorily to reviewer comments. Some minor grammatical issues remain but can be addressed while typesetting.

Summary of the article

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

The peer-reviewers found the topic being addressed in this manuscript to be important and challenging, and that a detailed commentary on oil sands process-affected water (OSPW) is a valuable contribution to the scientific literature. The “no further exposure” proposal was seen as important, and the six recommendations toward protecting human health and the environment were considered a useful framework for reconsidering how OSPW is currently managed. Recommendations for revision were minor. The authors responded comprehensively to the suggestions for changes to the manuscript and added some brief remarks on risk tolerance that the Editor judged not to require peer-review. The manuscript is therefore acceptable for publication.

Acceptance note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of peer-review that also included comments made during editorial triage. Only minor revisions were recommended, most of which were requests for clarification.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at [10.5281/zenodo.11038753](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11038753).